

Spectrophotometric Determination of Uranium by Galangin

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The use of 3, 5, 7-trihydroxyflavone (galangin) as an analytical reagent for the estimation of uranium has been investigated. The reagent forms a water-soluble orange complex with uranium. One to ten p. p. m. of uranium can be satisfactorily estimated spectrophotometrically at 450m μ , pH of the solutions being adjusted in the range 4.5 and 8.0. Molar composition of the complex has been found to be 1:1.

Several naturally occurring polyhydroxyflavones, viz., quercetin¹, morin²⁻⁴, and quercetin sulphonic acids⁵, have been investigated for the spectrophotometric estimation of uranium. Flavonol forms with uranyl ion a yellow complex which is sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. Spectrophotometric determination of uranium has been made by extracting this complex with tributyl⁶ phosphate⁶.

3,5,7-Trihydroxyflavone (galangin) forms a deep orange, water-soluble complex with uranium. The characteristics of the complex have been studied spectrophotometrically and its molar composition has been determined. The complex obeys Beer's law at 450 m μ to a concentration of 10 p. p. m. of uranium in the reaction mixture and uranium in quantities as low as 1 p.p.m. can be estimated spectrophotometrically between pH 4.5 and 8.0 by this reagent. The molar composition of the complex formed shows that it contains uranium and galangin in the molar ratio of 1:1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Galangin was obtained from the ether extract of the plant rhizomes of *Alpinia officinarum* Hance. Standard solutions of uranium were prepared by dissolving uranyl nitrate (A.R.) in distilled water. An ethanolic solution of galangin containing 0.270 g./litre ($M/1000$) was prepared. All other reagents employed were of A.R. quality. The absorption spectrum of galangin was taken using a Hilger UV spectrophotometer. All other spectrophotometric measurements were made using a Coleman spectrophotometer, model 14. All pH measurements were made with the help of a Metrohm pH-meter, type E 350.

1 Komenda, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 531.

2 Beck and Hantos, *Magyar Kem. Foly.*, 1954, 60, 244.

3 Almasy *et al.*, *Acta Chem. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1955, 7, 317.

4 Beak and Hantos, *ibid.*, 1955, 8, 233.

5 Kanno, *Japan Analyst*, 1959, 8, 633.

6 Kanno, *ibid.*, 1959, 8, 714.

Region of Maximum Absorption.—The absorption spectrum of galangin was taken in the ultraviolet as well as in the visible region. Maximum absorption was observed at 270 $m\mu$ and 360 $m\mu$. No absorption was observed in the visible region. The uranyl-galangin complex was found to have its absorption maximum at 450 $m\mu$. This wave length was therefore chosen in the subsequent investigations. The absorption spectra of the complex were also studied at various pH values (from 4.5 to 10.0) and the maximum was found to be near about 450 $m\mu$ in all these cases (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1. Absorption spectrum of uranyl-galangin complex.

FIG. 3.

Minimum Amount of the Reagent Required.—The optical densities of a series of solutions containing galangin and uranium in the molar ratio of 0.25:1 to 2:1 were determined at 450 $m\mu$. The results plotted (Fig. 3) show that there is a break showing complete formation of the complex. The molar ratio of galangin to uranium was, however, maintained at 5 in subsequent studies.

FIG. 2. Effect of pH on O.D. of uranyl-galangin complex soln.

FIG. 4. Lambert-Beer's law.

Effect of pH on Uranyl-galangin Complex.—It was found that the absorption by the complex was almost the same between pH 4.5 and 8.0 (Fig. 2). The decrease in the concentration of the complex at low pH may be due to the competition of hydrogen ions with uranyl ions for galangin, whereas the effect at high pH is probably due to the tendency of uranyl ions to combine with hydroxyl ions. The pH of the solutions was adjusted by the addition of very dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid.

Stability of the Colour of the Complex.—The colour of the complex was found to be stable and no change was observed even after keeping the complex for two weeks.

Beer-Lambert's Law.—The complex obeys the law up to a concentration of 10 p.p.m. of uranium at pH 8.0 (Fig. 4).

Molar Composition of the Complex.—Job's method⁷ of continued variations, as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁸, was employed for determination of the composition of the complex. Optical densities of solutions, prepared by mixing x ml of 1×10^{-3} M galangin solution with $(50-x)$ ml of 1×10^{-3} M uranyl salt solution, were determined at 450 m μ employing galangin solution of the corresponding strength as the reference solution. The absorption due to uranyl salt solution and galangin is negligible at 450 m μ . Hence the function y , defined as the difference between the optical density observed for a given mixture of the constituents and the corresponding optical densities of the respective components for no reaction, was taken in the present case as the observed optical density of the complex solution. The values of y are plotted against x (Fig. 5), the peak in the curve occurs when the molar ratio of galangin to uranyl ions is 1:1. The complex therefore has the molar composition $UO_2 \cdot M$, where M is a molecule of galangin. Molar composition studies of the complex by this method were also made at various pH values between 4.5 and 8.0 and in each case the composition was found to be 1:1. The molar composition of the uranyl-galangin complex was also verified by the slope-ratio method of Harvey and Manning⁹. For this purpose two series of solutions were prepared employing 1×10^{-3} M solutions of galangin and of uranium. In one series, uranium concentration was varied maintaining that of galangin constant and in sufficient excess. In the other series, galangin concentration was varied, maintaining that of uranium constant and in sufficient excess. The optical densities of the solutions of both series were determined at 450 m μ with aqueous

FIG. 5. Molar composition by Job's method.

7. Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

9. Harvey and Manning, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 448a.

ethanol as reference. The values obtained were plotted and curves P and Q (Fig. 6) were obtained. The curves are parallel to each other, thus having the same value for the slopes, which shows that the molar composition of the complex is 1:1.

FIG. 6. Molar composition by slope-ratio method.

That the molar composition of the complex is 1:1 is further confirmed by the curve in Fig. 3, which shows a sharp break at this composition.

Interferences due to Foreign Ions.—It was found that the anions like borate, thiosulphate, acetate, and chloride did not interfere even to the extent of 1000 p.p.m., whereas bromate, chlorate, sulphite, sulphate, persulphate, and citrate interfere appreciably at this concentration. Oxalate ions have been found to interfere seriously.

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